

Themeda triandra Red Grass

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Group: Monocot

Size: 0.3 - 1.5 metres in height.

Distribution:

This grass is widespread in South Africa, growing in undisturbed grasslands to savanna.

Importance:

Themeda triandra is a keystone grass species that plays an important role in maintaining healthy grassland ecosystems. It supports both livestock, such as cattle and native herbivores, making it central to wildlife conservation and livestock production.

PromethION Sequencing Report:

Output: 54.61 Gigabases

Approximate N50: 11.62 kilobases

Draft Genome Assembly Statistics:

Assembler used: Hifiasm

Genome Length: 0.7 Gigabases

BUSCO completeness score: 98.0% [Single: 77.6%, Duplicated: 20.4%]

BUSCO database: eukaryota

Assembly N50: 63 587.54 kilobases

Contig number: 3 166

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